

Subacute Toxicity Study of Total Alkaloids of Seeds of *Peganum harmala* in Female Rat

Authors : Mahdeb Nadia, Ghadjati Nadhra, Bettihi Sara, Daamouche Z. El Youm, Bouzidi Abdelouahab

Abstract : The effects of subacute administration of total alkaloids of seeds *Peganum harmala* were studied in female Albino-Wistar rats. After intraperitoneal administration of dose 50 mg/kg for 10 days and 40 mg/kg for 7 days of total alkaloids to the seeds of *Peganum harmala* (animal treatment lasted 17 days), there were remarkable changes in general appearance and deaths occurred in experimental group. After 17 days a significant reduction was observed in the surviving animals treated with total alkaloid seeds. The Red Blood Cells (RBC), Hematocrit (HCT), Hemoglobin (HGB) and White blood cells (WBCs), show significant reduction in the treated groups. There were no statistical differences in Glutamic-Oxaloacetic Transaminase (GOT), Glutamic-pyruvic Transaminase (GPT) and Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP), total protein, glucose and creatinine observed between groups. However the urea was significantly higher in the treated female rats than the control group. Histological examination of liver showed no histopathological changes. Alkaloids of *Peganum harmala* showed significant toxicity in female rats.

Keywords : *Peganum harmala*, rat, liver, kidney, alkaloids, toxicity

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